

transplanted in a randomized block design with three replications at 20×15-cm spacing. Observations from 10 randomly selected plants per replication in each genotype were recorded. Aroma was determined by using chopped leaves collected at 50% flowering stage.

GT is a measure of cooking ease and is indexed by the alkali digestibility test (Little et al 1958). It is measured by the alkali spreading value (ASV) of individual milled rice soaked in 1.7% KOH solution for 23 h at 30 °C using a 1–7 scale. A high rating indicates more disintegration and is classified under low GT. Rice varieties with intermediate GT (ASV of 3–5) are usually preferred over those with low GT (ASV of 6–7). The AC determines cooking behavior and eating quality of cooked rice. This was estimated and classified using a modi-

fication of Shen's method (1990), which was developed at the Cuttack Rice Research Institute (Swain and Nagaraju 1997). The GC test is a reliable index for cooked rice texture. A method modified by Cagampang (1973) was used to analyze the GC of 35 varieties. Length is classified as hard (6–10 mm), medium (11–20 mm), and soft (>20 mm).

Milled rice percentage was high for ADT42 (high-yielding variety RR380-10-3 (IET line), and Meenambur Local (scented rice). Percent head rice recovery was highest in IR50, TM95005, (MTU1029), and CSR27. ADT36 had the highest linear elongation among all genotypes. All scented varieties had intermediate (17–22%) AC and medium (11–20 mm) GC (data not shown), while the high-yielding, nonscented, and IET lines recorded higher

(>22%) AC and hard (6–10 mm) GC (data not shown). ADT36, ADRH1, HKR95-219, NWGR9, and NWGR13 showed normal milled rice percentage and head rice recovery, long slender grains, intermediate GT, hard GC, and high AC.

References

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Performance of prototype rice lines from ideotype breeding

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Several new plant type (NPT) rice breeding lines for the irrigated ecosystem have been developed at JNAU from crosses IR47705-AC5/ChIR87-3-1//Kranti (the 57K series), IR47705-AC5/IR32307-75-1-3-1//Kranti (the 63K series), and IR47705-AC5/IR28211-45-1-1-2//Kranti (the 72K series). These were based on a basic ideotype of rice (Janoria 1989).

We evaluated 16 NPT lines with three checks—MW10, IR36, and Kranti—during the 1996-97 dry (December-May) and wet (June-November) seasons at RARS. The two field experiments were laid out in a randomized block design with three replications, 6 × 1.2-m net plot size, and 20 × 20-cm spacing, and with 100-60-40 kg NPK ha⁻¹.

Five plants were randomly sampled per plot for plant height, panicle number

plant⁻¹, and grain number panicle⁻¹. Grain yield (t ha⁻¹) was estimated from net plots of 7.2 m² and days to maturity and 1,000-grain weight on a plot basis.

The top-yielding NPT lines in the early and medium maturity groups—NPT63K-1-20 and NPT63K-12-51, respectively—significantly ($P = 0.05$) outyielded the respective checks (see table) in both seasons. NPT57K-3-6 (very early) had a yield similar to its check MW10 during the wet season. NPT lines generally had a much higher grain number panicle⁻¹, lower panicle number plant⁻¹, and greater plant height than the semidwarf checks in accordance with the ideotype design.

The top-yielding NPT line (NPT63K-12-51) was resistant to bacterial leaf blight (caused by *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae*) and sheath blight (caused by

Rhizoctonia solani f. sp. *sasakii*), the two major constraints to yield in Madhya Pradesh under artificial inoculation.

The longer duration of experimental entries in the dry season was due to lower temperatures during December and January, which slowed seedling growth in the nursery. Hence, seedling age at transplanting was 50 d in the dry season compared with 21 d in the wet season. Similarly, higher photothermal regimes during the postplanting phase reduced plant height and increased yields in the dry season.

Reference

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Performance of top new plant type breeding lines of very early, early, and medium maturity groups, RARS, Bilaspur, India, 1996 wet season (WS) and dry season (DS).

Entry	Days to maturity		Plant height (cm)		Panicles plant ⁻¹ (no.)		Grains panicle ⁻¹ (no.)		1,000-grain weight (g)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	
	WS	DS	WS	DS	WS	DS	WS	DS	WS	WS	DS
<i>Very early</i>											
NPT57K-3-6	107	137	114	85	6.7	8.7	163	207	25.1	6.4	7.7
MW10 (check)	105	138	92	79	9.3	10.0	111	121	22.7	5.2	5.6
<i>Early</i>											
NPT63K-1-20	118	143	107	86	6.7	7.3	205	260	28.2	7.4	8.2
IR36 (check)	116	142	82	72	10.0	11.0	126	139	22.8	5.7	7.2
<i>Medium</i>											
NPT63K-12-51	127	152	117	100	9.3	9.3	228	271	28.6	9.2	9.9
Kranti	128	146	106	86	11.3	11.3	129	164	28.1	6.5	7.5
LSD (0.05)	—	—	8.6	6.5	2.0	2.3	40.4	46.1	—	1.5	1.6

VL Dhan 61, a new rice variety for the northwestern Himalayan region

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A new rice variety, VL Dhan 61, was released by the Central Varietal Release Committee in 1997 for cultivation under irrigated transplanted conditions of hilly and valley areas (up to 1,150 m) of Uttar Pradesh and Himachal Pradesh. VL Dhan 61 was developed to combine high yield and blast resistance from the cross Jaya/Ta-poo-cho-z, using the pedigree method. Eighty-two desirable plants were selected in the F₂ generation in 1986. Further selection was made until uniformity was achieved.

VL Dhan (IET13485) was tested in the 1992-95 All-India Coordinated Trials at different hill sites. It yielded an average of 4.9 t ha⁻¹—16% higher than zonal check Himdhan, 22% higher than the state/local check, and 6% higher than the high-yielding test genotype (Table 1). It is a nonlodging, semitall (110 cm) variety with 130-135 d duration. It has compact, well-exserted long panicles with good spikelet fertility and long bold grains (length/breadth, 2.65). It has also shown resistance to/tolerance for prevailing biotic stresses (leaf and neck blast, stem borer) and tolerance for abiotic constraints (low temperature) (Table 2).

Table 1. Grain yield (t ha⁻¹) of VL Dhan 61, All-India Coordinated Trials, hill zone, 1992-95.

Genotype	1992	1993	1994	1995	Mean	Gain (%)
VL Dhan 61 (IET13485)	4.8	3.6	5.0	6.2	4.9	—
Himdhan (zonal check)	4.2	3.2	2.7	4.8	4.2	16
State check	3.7	2.9	4.1	5.3	4.0	22
VL 89-1167 (IET13483)	4.1	3.2	4.8	5.6	4.4	11
VL 89-1177 (IET13484)	4.6	3.4	5.0	5.5	5.6	6

Table 2. Comparison of newly released variety VL Dhan 61 with its parents.

Character	VL Dhan 61	Parents	
		Jaya	Ta-poo-cho-z
Days to 50% flowering	103–105	100	109
Days to maturity	130–135	131	140
Plant height (cm)	110	85	90
Panicle type	Compact	Compact	Compact
Panicle length (cm)	25.5	25.2	22.0
Awn	Tip awned	Awnless	Awn
Panicle exertion	Well	Well	Well
Threshability	Easy	Moderate	Hard
1,000-grain weight (g)	23.4	25.0	23.0
Milling (%)	65.8	74.0	60.3
Kernel length (mm)	6.68	6.27	5.14
Kernel breadth (mm)	2.52	2.54	2.69
L/B (length/breadth)	2.65	2.47	1.91
Grain shape	Long bold	Long bold	Short bold
Alkali digestion value	5.2	7.0	—
Disease and insect score (0–9 score) ^a			
Leaf blast	4	—	2
Neck blast	3	5	3
False smut	3	—	—
Stem borer	3	—	—
Leaffolder	5	—	—

^aMaximum score recorded using Standard evaluation system for rice.